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CORPORATE GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE AND EARNINGS QUALITY OF LISTED AGRICULTURAL COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Corporate governance plays a vital role in ensuring transparency, accountability and the reliability of financial reporting in organizations. The study examined the effect of corporate governance structure and earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria. The study being correlations research on a board level, adopted an ex-post~ factor research design. The population of the study comprise of all the five companies in the Nigerian exchange group. Since the population is not large, the study intends to cover all the five listed agricultural companies, thus the population size is the same as the sample size. Thus, data was collected from the financial reports of five listed agricultural companies in the Nigerian exchange group as at the time of the research and analyzed using ordinary least square panel regression. Findings from the study indicated that board size has a significant effect on the earnings quality of agricultural companies in Nigeria, board independence has no significant effect on the earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria, board female gender diversity has no significant effect on the earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria. Hence, the study recommended the need for: comprehensive evaluation of corporate governance systems of companies, more levels of board independence, review and strengthen the composition and role of the audit committee especially as regard their monitoring and over sight function on the financial reports so as to improve the earnings quality of companies among others.

INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance plays a vital role in ensuring transparency, accountability and the reliability of financial reporting in organizations. In the agricultural sector, corporate governance is particularly important due to the sector's contributions to Nigeria's economy, food security, and employment generation. Listed agricultural companies are expected to uphold strong corporate governance structures to enhance earnings quality and maintain investor confidence.

Earnings quality refers to the accuracy, reliability, and sustainability of reported earnings. High-quality earnings provide a true reflection of a firm's financial performance, while low-quality earnings may result from earnings management practices such as income

smoothing and earnings manipulation. In Nigeria, concerns about weak corporate governance practices in the agricultural sector have raised questions about the reliability of financial reports.

Recent studies (Adebayo & Adekoya, 2023, Ogunleye & Ojo, 2024) indicate that weak governance structures, poor audit mechanisms, and regulatory inefficiencies contribute to low earnings quality among Nigerian agricultural companies. Furthermore, corporate governance structures mechanisms such as board independence, audit committee effectiveness, and ownership structure have been found to influence financial reporting quality (Okonkwo *et al.*, 2023).

The Implementation of the Sarbanes-Oxley (SOX) Act of 2002 in the United States led other countries to realize the significance of quality corporate governance mechanisms implementation in lowering agency costs and maximizing shareholders wealth. This realization ignited several studies in emerging economies to investigate the impact of corporate governance (Agyeman 2020). To fully achieve the stated objectives of corporate enterprises, there is a need for separation of controls through corporate governance mechanism functions as strategic decision-makers (Tensen, 1986).

Despite the significant importance of corporate governance on accounting information quality, it has received less attention in the literature; particularly for emerging economies like Nigeria. This coupled with the use of a single measurement, in already existing studies which is likely to present unreliable results since it is inadequate to measure corporate governance with a single measure, creating a policy gap such that policy makers and firm owners do not have adequate information in decisions regarding the significance or otherwise of corporate governance in influencing earnings quality and the necessary measures needed.

Despite the regulatory frameworks established by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FCRN) and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), listed agricultural companies in Nigeria continue to face governance-related challenges that impact earnings quality. Instances of financial misstatements, profit manipulation, and weak oversight have been reported in recent years (Chinedu & Ibrahim, 2024).

The problem this study seeks to address is the extent to which corporate governance mechanisms influence earnings quality in Nigeria's listed agricultural companies. Prior research has examined corporate governance in various industries, but limited attention has been given to the agricultural sector. Understanding this relationship is crucial for improving financial transparency and investor confidence.

The concept of earnings quality, though subject to varied interpretations, fundamentally seeks to bolster the credibility of financial information disclosed in corporate financial reports. Krishan Prasa (2006) explained earnings quality to comprise the extent to which the reported earnings of an entity go to represent its actual economic reality. So, the need for the corporate governance structures of companies to predict the earnings quality of the firm becomes a subject of interest in academics and accounting research.

The Nigerian economy has experienced turbulent times concerning their corporate governance practices resulting in generally lower corporate profits across the economy. Arising from high profile firm failures and distresses, coupled with generally poor performance, across markets sectors, the credibility of the existing corporate governance mechanism amongst African markets have been put into question. (Amidu, 2007). The

numerous corporate governance scandals in the past decade in some African countries, notably Nigeria and Ghana, limited the success of regulatory reforms hindering the effectiveness of implementing quality corporate governance mechanisms. According to [Fodio, Ibikunle and Oba \(2013\)](#), cases of corporate failures are an indictment of the effectiveness of the existing corporate governance structures coupled with numerous corruptions in these countries. Both public and private sector corporate managers manipulate and adjust financial reports to lure investors. A clear example is a situation that occurred in Nigeria at the beginning of 2008 stated in the African corporate Governance Network of 2016, that by the beginning of 2008 Nigeria exchange group had become significantly overvalued with a price-earnings ratio of 57 considered highest in the world at that time.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study examined the corporate governance and earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria. The specific objective seeks:

- i. to ascertain the effect of board size on earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria
- ii. To determine the effect of board independence on earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria.
- iii. to examine the effect of board gender and diversity on earnings quality of agricultural companies in Nigeria
- iv. to examine the effect of audit committee size on earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Corporate Governance

Corporate governance refers to the system by which companies are directed and controlled ([OECD, 2023](#)), it involves mechanisms such as board structure, ownership concentration, audit quality and regulatory compliance. Good governance enhances financial reporting quality and reduces earning management ([Fodio et al, 2022](#)).

In Nigeria the security and exchange commission (SEC) Provides corporate governance guidelines for listed companies. However studies suggest that compliance in the agricultural sector remains weak due to inadequate regulatory enforcement ([Adebayo & Adekoya, 2023](#)).

The concept of corporate governance constantly remains an important issue as far as businesses are concerned. It is a topical issue in modern management and other related disciplines that gained more prominence since the well-celebrated Eron and Whatcom scandals in the United States. Various scholars have different definitions of corporate governance from different perspectives that reflect their varied interests and backgrounds. It is an area that has enjoyed robust attention and thus several definitions of the concept exist in extant literature. According to Cadbury, Corporate Governance is concerned with holding the balance between economic and social goals and between individual and communal goals. The Department of Economic and Community Development defined Corporate Governance as a system by which businesses are directed and controlled "This definition perhaps remains the simplest.

Elements of Corporate Governance

There are also essential elements that must be put into consideration to achieve excellence and the desired goals and objectives. Corporate governance is effective when the essential elements are efficiency deployed and implemented to achieve the set of goals of the organization. Forsy (2018) identified six essential elements of effective corporate governance as the board of directors independence and performance. A focus on diversity, regular compensation review and management. Auditor independence and transparency, shareholder rights and takeover provisions and proxy voting and shareholders influence.

Board of directors independence and performance: Board members are the fiduciaries where the organization towards a sustainable future by adopting sound, ethical and legal governance and financial management policies as well as by making sure that a firm has adequate resources to advance its

Board size: it is always good to maintain adequate board size but there is no set number of members for board most boards range from 3-31 members while the board of directors recommended size is seven. According to Onalo et al (2017) the optimal number of directors for boards to make a decision is seven.

Board independence: independence occurs when a board member shall not be and is not currently employed by the company or its auditor and the board members employers does not have a significant amount of business with the company. An independent board director is someone who does not have a material or pecuniary relationship with the company either directly or through one of the company's partners, shareholders or management members except for the fees it gets from being a board member (Vieira, 2019).

Board gender diversity: Board gender diversity is a significant aspect of corporate governance; it is defined as the presence of female directors on the board of directors of corporations (Carter, 2003). Board gender diversity for this study deals with the female to male ratio of the board. There is the argument that the female presence on the board introduces some dynamics in board interactions and this can ultimately affect the outcomes at the board level decisions regarding earnings quality (Agyeman, 2020).

Board of directors meetings: A board meeting is meeting of a company's board of directors, held usually at certain times of the year to discuss companywide policies or issues. The board of directors determines the overall business strategy of the company, and the directors are either elected by shareholders or members of the organization. Effective board meetings help a company to work out a business strategy and to execute it successfully. It aims at determining members of the board, non-executive directors, board papers, running the meeting, follow up to the meeting and improving board skills.

Earnings Quality

Earning quality refers to the accuracy and reliability of reported financial performance. Highly-quality earnings provide useful information for decision-making, while low-quality earnings often result from earnings management practices like income smoothing (Healy & Wahlen, 2023).

Earnings represent the net income resulting from operations of a corporation and it is the basis for computing the tax liability of the entity. Thus earnings are indicators for assessing the financial performance of a company (Francis, Ryan, Oisson, and Schipper, 2003) with an emphasis on the concept of earnings quality Ehen, Jory and NGO (2019) note

that earnings quality can be defined as the predictive ability of reported earnings to future earnings. In other words, earning can be categorized as having higher quality if previous earnings can be used to predict future earnings. This is one of the reasons accounting standards are constantly being updated to improve the quality of reported earnings that is free from manipulation (Dechow, Ge and Schrand, 2010)

However, the concept of earnings quality is multidimensional and can be understood from several perspectives. First, there is earnings management which is act of intentionally influencing the process of financial reporting to obtain some private gain. Second is earnings persistence which focuses largely in the continuity and durability of the current earnings. The third earnings quality dimension is the earnings predictability which kicks at the predictive characteristics of earnings. All three dimensions are important and present unique perspectives on earning quality. This view of earnings quality is also shared by Agyeman (2020) who pointed out that earnings have good quality if earnings in the current period can be used to forecast the possible earnings in the future period.

Corporate Governance and Earnings Quality Issues in the Agricultural Sector of Nigeria

Several Corporate governance mechanisms influence earnings quality in Nigeria's agricultural companies:

Board Independence: Companies with a higher proportion of independence directors tend to have more reliable financial reports (Yusuf, 2024)

Audit Committee: A well-structured audit committee strengthens financial oversight and improves earnings quality (Uchenna et al, 2023).

Ownership Structure: Institutional Ownership enhances monitoring, reducing opportunities earnings management (Bello et al, 2023).

Regulatory compliance: compliance with the financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) guidelines is linked to better earnings quality (Owolab & Adeyemi, 2024).

Nwafor (2002) opined that agricultural companies, similarly to companies in other economic sectors thrive under effective corporate governance through adequate board size, board gender diversity and broad duality. The study suggest that agricultural companies in Nigeria will improve their productivity levels through efficient governance thereby highlighting the possibility of agricultural companies competing favorably with their counterparts in other sectors in terms of profitability. This implies that agribusiness can become an attractive investment opportunity in the Nigerian capital market if the corporate governance issues are equally given serious attention.

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory of Corporate Governance

Agency theory was propounded by Jensen in 2010. Agency theory posits that corporations act as agents of its stakeholders. This statement of the theory implies that shareholders investing corporate ownership and thereby entrust their resources to the management of directors and officers of the corporation. The theory focuses on relationships between parties, how one delegates some decision -making authority to the other. Just like masses elect political representatives to run a country in such a way that maximizes their interests. In the same way, shareholders in business companies elect members of board and board of directors, and entrust their resources to the management of these appointed directors to run the companies in ways to maximize their interest.

Agency theory is a principle as well as a verifiable tool in use to explain and resolve issues in the relationship between business principles and their agents. This is a relationship that is between the shareholders as principals and the board of directors/members (company executives) as the agent (Jason, 2021). The theory relates to the present study that studies corporate governance as one of the major variables. This study is anchored on agency theory which provides a framework for understanding the dynamics between shareholders and corporate management, it is not without its criticism. Critics argue that the theory tends to oversimplify the complexities of corporate governance relationship, assuming a one-size-fits-all model. The emphasis on shareholder wealth maximization may lead to short term decision making at the expense of long-term sustainability. Additionally, the theory may not fully account for the diverse interest and motivations of various stakeholders beyond shareholders, such as employees, customers and the broader community. Some Scholars advocate for a more inclusive approach to corporate governance that considers a wide range of stakeholders and incorporates ethical considerations. Despite these critiques, agency theory remains a widely used and influential framework for analyzing corporate governance practices and their impact on earnings quality.

Empirical Review

A Study by Chinedu & Ibrahim (2024) found that companies with strong governance structure report more conservative earning, reducing earnings manipulation. In the same line of thought, Owolabi & Adeyemi (2024) observed that regulatory reforms have improved financial reporting quality in Nigeria's agricultural sectors, through challenges persist.

Ikebujo and Anusionwu (2022) examined the history of corporate governance in Nigeria, alongside the efforts made to develop corporate governance in Nigeria, alongside the efforts made to develop a corporate governance framework that will stand the test of time considering the recent issuance of the Nigerian code of corporate governance 2018. They considered issues which the corporate governance framework faces in Nigeria ranging from institutional challenges, corruption, poor corporate governance culture, multiplicity of codes on corporate governance and weak regulatory mechanisms to protection of whistle-blowers with the aim of ascertaining the main challenge of our corporate governance framework. The work intended to find out if the problem of Nigeria corporate governance is actually in adequacy of laws or ineffective implementation of recommendations by the codes. Their finding shows that Nigeria's corporate laws and codes on corporate governance is viable and thus concluded that the challenges that come with the practicability of corporate governance in Nigeria require of the codes and effective implementations of the recommendations of the codes and effective implementations of the recommendations of the codes and effective monitoring. Thus, the study portrays the essentiality of enabling the environment if the gain of corporative governance mechanism must be realized.it also highlights the need for the national government to rid the system of corruption at least to the barest minimum.

Zalata, Ntim, Alsohagy & malagila (2022) studied gender diversity and earnings management in consideration of female directors with financial background. The result obtained from their study showed that the participation of female directors with relevant financial background relates positively with earnings quality more than the participation of female directors without such background. Date was collected for the period of 2007 and runs for 2013 person correlation matrix was used for the analysis. Findings from the researchers suggested that only female directors possessing relevant financial background

and having fewer outside directorships are able to mitigate earnings management and therefore oiler committing expert female directors with more outside directorships would diminish their monitoring ability. The researchers did not find any evidence to show that female without relevant financial background are able to mitigate earnings management, irrespective of their outside directorships or tenure. The finding diversity to harness the benefits from board diversity.

[Madhusa and kehelwalatenna \(2021\)](#) studied corporate governance and earnings quality using the discretionary accrual approach. The study attempt to add to the body flow approaches in measuring earnings quality. The study was domiciled in Sri Lanka using secondary data from 51 food and beverages listed companies. Ordinary least square multiple regression was used as the analytical procedure.it uncolored that corporate governance through only three variables: board of directors the audit quality and firm size has a significant effect on earning quality so they concluded that regulatory efforts made to initiate and install corporate governance in the and beverages industry are yet to results in better corporate performance. The study therefore identifies board size as the significant contributor of corporate governance towards earnings quality in Sri Lanka.

[Yakob and Hasan \(2021\)](#) researched the effects of board meetings on information disclosure and firm financial performance in Malaysian publicly traded companies. It explored the theoretical foundation of the agency theory as it relates to the corporate governance function and examined all nonfinancial companies listed on the main market of burial Malaysia between 2013 and 2017. They employed quantitative date analysis and numerical representations of empirical findings to identify and explain the evidence. The findings dedicate that the firm relationship between earnings and financial performance, measured by TobinQ and return on equity, may be significantly affected by board meeting. So far, previous studies have evidence the criticality of board size, board gender diversity, and board meetings as indicators of corporate governance in firm's reporting.

Furthermore, [Mohammed and Kurawa \(2021\)](#) examined the mediating effect of earnings quality on the relationship between corporate board attributes and the value of listed insurance companies in Nigeria. The study utilized secondary source of data collected from annual reports of the sampled companies for the period 2008 to 2018. The population of the study comprises all twenty-seven. Insurance companies listed on the Nigerian exchange group, out of which fifteen were selected as study sample. Descriptive and Pearson correlation analysis were used for the analysis. Path analysis using structure equation modeling was used; also Monte Carlo's test was employed to determine the significance of the indirect effect. It was found that board size, board meetings and women directorship significantly affect firm value. The researchers revealed that board size and board independence significantly affect earnings quality of listed insurance companies in Nigeria. Furthermore, the study found that earnings quality does not significantly mediate the relationship between board size, board independence, women director, board meetings and firm value. Hence the study concluded that the direct association between boards attributes mechanism and firm value is more crucial than their indirect association mediated by earnings quality. The study therefore lists board independence as having a significant effect on earnings quality on insurance companies in Nigeria.

[Raya \(2021\)](#) attempted to find empirical evidence for the role of earnings quality as a mediator between good corporate governance (GCG) mechanism and firm performance. Descriptive statistical analysis methods, data normality test, classical assumption test and

hypothesis test are used in this study. The sample is 570 data manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia stock exchange from 2015 to 2019. This research used multiple regression analysis. The result showed that the proportion of independent board of commissioners and audit committee expertise does not affect earnings quality.

[Saleh, Afifa and Alsufy \(2020\)](#) investigated the importance of earnings quality as a determinant of companies' performance. It provides some empirical evidence from an emerging market, especially from the Jordanian market. The study developed an econometric model for the effect of earnings quality on the companies' performance using empirical evidence. It employed a panel data analysis method by using a sample of all Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies listed on Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) during 2010-2018. The results revealed that return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and earnings per share (EPS) as proxies of a company's performance are affected by the earnings quality. This provides the importance of positive earnings quality that eventually influences the companies' performance. The results of this study suggest that the higher control level on the manager's behavior and its outcome will have an effect on earnings quality, and thus the company's performance increases. The research illuminates the role of earnings quality in improving the lot of the reporting firm though it is outside the study focus of this present work.

[Wu, et al \(2020\)](#), investigated the long-run effect of corporate governance mechanism on earnings management of listed companies in Nigeria and Ghana.

They used Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) in establishing a long-run effect of good corporate mechanism in reducing earnings management practice by corporate managers. ACO selected four major corporate governance mechanisms. Board procedure index, board disclosure index, ownership structure index, and shareholder's rights index, these were the key corporate governance mechanism that influence the reduction in earnings management activities. KNN produced a strong significant longitudinal effect of implementing good corporate governance mechanisms in decreasing the manipulating behavior of managers. Apart from the change in analytical procedure introduced by these researchers, they also approached earnings quality by considering the extent of manipulations in the financial report which is termed earnings management.

[Olaoye and Adewumi \(2020\)](#) examined the impact of corporate governance on earnings quality in listed companies in Nigeria. The study sampled thirty-seven quoted manufacturing companies for period 2011-2017. It found out that board size, board independence and board gender diversity has a significant impact on earnings quality in addition, corporate governance variables appear to be quite sensitive to the measure of earnings quality used. Based on the findings, the study recommends the need for comprehensive evaluation of corporate governance systems of companies and the need for more level of board independence. The diversity issue though is gaining momentum in corporate governance literature can still be regarded as not as dominant as compared to others especially as it relates to protecting shareholder rights and framing dividend policy. The authors however, failed to include other measures of corporate governance to the model used in their study.

[Ado, Norfadzilah, Mustapha, and Ademola \(2020\)](#) explored the financial determinants of earnings management and profitability of listed companies in Nigeria using a panel data approach on eighty-four listed companies on the NSE with 756 firms - year

observations for the period 2010-2018 financial years. The study employs a secondary method to retrieve data from annual statements of listed companies and Thompson Reuters Data Stream. Analysis of data was done using multiple regression and results show that earnings ability has a significant and positively related to the profitability, which was measured using returns on assets. This result indicates that the more earnings ability of a company, the profitability of the listed companies in Nigeria will increase. Financial structure ability has a significant negative association with the returns on assets. This further indicates that any increase in financial structure ability, profitability of listed companies in Nigeria could also increase in the same value. Furthermore, the statistical results offered evidence that non-financial factors are positively and significantly associated with the ROA. The authors concluded that companies that engaged in earnings management are also seen to be more profitable.

[Agyeman \(2020\)](#) looked at the factors that influence earnings management practice of financial institutions located on the Ghana Stock Exchange from the period 2010-2018. He adopted quantitative design and collected data on total accrual, firm size, firm age, leverage, auditor size, and firm age which were sourced from the published annual report of nine (9) financial institutions listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange from 2008-2018. Results from the regression model significance level shows that board size and financial leverage are the factors influencing earnings management practice amongst listed financial institutions. Results from the correlation model also yield a negative correlation between auditor size, financial leverage and earnings management while board size, firm size, and firm age reveal a positive correlation with earnings management. The study contradicts the findings made by [Nu et al \(2020\)](#) on the role of corporate governance on earnings management practices though later considered companies from both Nigeria and Ghana.

[Hashim \(2019\)](#) studied board diversity and earnings quality by examining the role internal audit as a moderator. The study explored the relationships between board diversity and the earnings quality of the companies listed in Bursa Malaysia main market.

[Asogwa, Ofrengu Nnam and Chukwunwike \(2019\)](#) examined the effect of corporate governance leadership models and attributes on firm's earnings quality using evidence from Nigeria quoted companies. The study used an export factor design with a two-stage multiple random and fixed effect regression analysis. A sample of 37 quoted companies in the Nigerian Exchange Group between 2014 and 2018 was selected for the study findings from the study are relative to unitary corporate leadership; dual board leadership model outperformed and significantly improves earnings persistence and value relevance. Earnings persistence and value relevance increased in boards where CEOs and board chairpersons have equal financial expertise. Also the quality of earnings improved significantly with a good mix of financial expertise and legal skills in the board. Thus, the capital market places a premium on such a good leadership attribute mix. This study concentrated on non-financial companies in Nigeria and made an original contribution to the effect of corporate governance on earnings persistence and predictability and how the market reacts to certain attributes combinations. It is important to note that the study cut across various industries in the Nigerian market but only excluded financial companies.

METHODOLOGY

The study being correlations research on a board level, adopted an ex-post factor research design. The study is deemed to be correlational because it investigated the association between corporate governance indicators raised in this study and ratio of earnings

quality. On the other hand, the study adopted ex-post facto design as it examined the objectives of the study raised using secondary data which are already captured in the financial reports of the listed agriculture companies without interference of any sort.

The population of the study comprise of all the five companies in the Nigerian exchange group. Since the population is not large, the study intends to cover all the five listed agricultural companies, thus the population size is the same as the sample size.

The Companies are:

1. Okomu oil palm plc. (Okumu-udo ovia south west LGA, Benin-Edo State Nigeria)
2. Euah Lakes plc. (Port-Harcourt, Rivers State Nigeria)
3. FTN Cocoa Processors plc. (Magodo GRA, Lagos state)
4. Livestock feeds plc. (Ikeja, Lagos state Nigeria)
5. Presco plc. (Ikpoba - Okha LGA, Benin-Edo state)

The study utilized secondary sources of data to conduct the analysis of this work.

Thus, data was collected from the financial reports of five listed agricultural companies in the Nigerian exchange group as at the time of the research. The data that represents the variables identified in this work was calculated from the information contained in the financial reports of each of the companies for the ten years covered in the study, i.e. 2014-2024

The study examined the relationship that exist between corporate governance indicators and earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria using ordinary least square panel regression. However a panel in this work was preceded by some preliminary test to determine the adequacy of the intended technique. These tests include the descriptive analysis, cross-sectional dependency tests, unit root test and co-integration.

Model Specification

The study adapted model of [Olaoye and Adewumi \(2020\)](#) which was stated as:

$$EQ = a + 1BS + 2BIND + 3BGD + 4ACS+t$$

Where

BS = board size

BIND = board gender diversity

ACS = audit committee size

t = stochastic Error Term

Hence the study adapted and specified its model as follows;

Mathematical Model:

Earnings Quality Ratio = F (Board size + Board Independence + Board gender diversity + Audit committee size)

Econometric Model:

$$EQR_{it} = + 1BSZ_{it} + 2BID_{it} + 3BGD_{it}$$

EQR-Earnings quality (is explained in this study as the degree of the smoothness of the reported earnings in relation to the volume of operations. It is measured as Earnings divided by cash flow from operating activities multiplied by 100%)

Thus, $EQR = (\text{Profit before tax} / \text{Cash flow from operating activities}) \times (100/1)$

BGD = Board gender diversity (the number of female board members divided by the total number of members on the board)

BSZ = board size (Total number of members represented on the board)

BID = Board Independence (Number of Non-executive members on the board divided by the total number of board members)

ACS = Audit committee size (is the total members in the audit committee team)

it = 1 Cross - section & time

= Beta coefficient of the model.

Decision rule: to accept the null hypothesis if the calculated probability value is greater than the significant probability value of 0.05 (5%)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of data extracted from the financial reports of the five listed companies in the agricultural sector were analyzed, presented and discussed in the subsequent sections of this chapter with the aim of achieving the objectives of this research project.

Descriptive Analysis

The corporate governance characteristics and earnings quality proxies extracted from the financial reports of the companies for the ten years period formed a long panel studies data.

Table 1: Results of Descriptive Analysis

	AUDIT_COMMITTEE_SIZE	BOARD_FEMALE_GENDER_DIVERSITY	BOARD_INDEPENDENCE	BOARD_SIZE	LOG_EARNINGS
Mean	5.122449	8.985306	69.42816	8.510204	-0.171140
Median	6.000000	10.00000	71.43000	9.000000	-0.183776
Maximum	7.000000	33.33000	87.50000	12.00000	1.689564
Minimum	3.000000	0.000000	42.86000	3.000000	-1.541720
Std. Dev.	1.166059	9.418782	12.08025	2.151767	0.609745
Skewness	-0.638121	0.692823	-0.387355	-0.426098	0.204767
Kurtosis	2.204763	2.481491	2.339125	2.531859	4.130093
Jarque-Bera	4.616611	4.468940	2.117070	1.930181	2.949861
Probability	0.099430	0.107049	0.346964	0.380949	0.228795
Sum	251.0000	440.2800	3401.980	417.0000	-8.385847
Sum Sq. Dev.	65.26531	4258.245	7004.762	222.2449	17.84587
Observations	50	50	50	50	50

Source: Research Analyses Output

Furthermore, the first part of the analyses consists of the descriptive analyses of the various series, which were taken to assess the measure of variability and normality of the series, which will also serve as a means of determining the appropriate method of further data analysis. Table 1 contains the results of the descriptive analyses of the five series: audit

committee size, board female gender diversity, board independence, board size and earnings quality.

Audit committee size of the companies ranged from the minimum of three members to seven members with a median value of six suggesting that majority of the companies in this sector across the ten years covered by the study may have audit committee size higher than the minimum value of three. The standard deviation value also aligns with the above stance as its value of 1.17 for the range suggests that the deviation of the observations from the mean is small. The probability of the Jarque-Bera statistics, which served as the measure of ascertaining the normality of the data distribution in this study, is more than 5% for audit committee size thus the study accepts that audit committee size as a series is normally distributed.

Board female gender diversity as another measure of corporate governance structure has a different behavior as it ranges from 0% – 33% with a median value of 10% which suggests that at least half of the observation points of the companies that formed the panel cross-section board for female gender diversity are equal to, or less than 10%. This is also supported by the high standard deviation indicating that the range of the series is wider and the observation points' deviation from the mean is high. The board female gender diversity has a normal distribution as the Jarque-Bera probability has a value of more than 5%.

Board independence of the panel data analyzed in table 1 appears to be fairly dispersed as it ranges from lowest value of 42.86 to 87.50 with associating median value 71.43 and a standard deviation of 12.08 approximately. It is notable that the median value suggests that half of the observation points are more inclined to the maximum value since the median value data is higher than half of the range of the observations. It implies that the companies in the agricultural sector possess higher board independence across the number of years covered in this thesis. The data distribution of board independence is adjudged to be normally distributed based on the outcome of Jarque-Bera value of 2.11 and probability of 35% approximately.

The board size presents mean and median value of 9 approximately whereas it ranges from minimum membership of 3 to maximum membership of 12 across the ten years covered by the study and amongst the listed companies in the sector. The median of 9 therefore suggests that the observation points for this variable are tilted more towards the maximum value since the median value is farther from the minimum than it is to the maximum point. The series is normally distributed having a Jarque-Bera value of 1.93 and probability outcome of 38%.

The earnings quality presented in its logged form ranged from the minimum value of -1.54 to the maximum value of 1.69 approximately. The median value of -0.18 approximately shows that the observations may be tilted to the minimum value though its large standard deviation of 0.61 approximately suggests that the series are widely dispersed around the mean. This is also consistent with the large ranges of the observation points. Furthermore, the series is normally distributed having a Jarque-Bera value of 2.95 and probability of 23% approximately. Note that earnings quality of the panel in its raw failed the test of normality as shown in appendix 1 before the descriptive analysis of the series was taken again in its logged form as contained in table 1.

Having described the tendencies, dispersion and normality of the data distributions; the study proceeds to the next level of its diagnostic tests as shown in the next section of this chapter.

Cross-Section Dependence Tests of Variables

As part of the pre-estimation tests, the study conducts a cross-section dependence test in order to correctly specify the unit root procedure that will be applicable in ascertaining the stationarity or otherwise of the individual series.

Table 2: Cross-section dependence test results

Test Criteria	Audit_Committee size	Board_Female_Gender_Diversity	Board_Independence	Board_Size	Log_Earnings_Quality
Breusch-Pagan LM	0.0728	0.8907	0.0003	0.0196	0.6512
Pesaran scaled LM	0.1139	0.2642	0.0000	0.0121	0.6181
Bias-corrected scaled LM	0.1925	0.1633	0.0000	0.256	0.4376
Pesaran CD	0.0302	0.8876	0.0000	0.2234	0.6715
Decision on unit root generation	1 st Generation	1 st Generation	2 nd Generation	1 st Generation	1 st Generation
Method of Unit root	LLC	LLC	Im, Pesaran & Shin W	LLC	LLC

Source: Research Analyses Output extracted

This is done by conducting panel cross-section dependence test for each of the variable series. The results obtained are attached as appendix 2(a) – 2(d) whereas the probability values for each of the variables are presented on table 2. The probability values are reported for each of the criterion and the decision taken for each of the variable is also reported in the last row of the tables.

The results shown table 2 indicate that audit committee size, female board gender diversity, board size and earnings quality all possess probability values of more 5% for at least one of the criteria variables possess probability values of above 5% for all the test criteria hence the decision to adopt 1st generation unit root method which is Levin, Lin, and Chu t.

However, for board independence, the results of the probability values for all the test criteria all yield values of less than 5% suggesting the rejection of null hypothesis which proposes that there is no cross-dependence for board independence as a variable. Thus, this outcome informed the decision to apply a method from the 2nd generation unit root methods in subsequent stationary estimation of the variable using Im, Pesaran and Shin W estimation method specifically.

Panel Unit Root Test Estimation

As part of the pre-estimation tests, the panel unit root test was conducted to understand the sufficiency of adopting ordinary least squares method as the data analysis technique for the model which is intended to analyze the effect of corporate governance structure on earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria. The essence is to avoid the use of data series, which are not stationary at level in the ordinary least square estimation method as it will not be appropriate to use this method. The results of the panel

unit root estimation conducted for all the variables in this study are attached as appendices 3(a) – 3(e) and also summarized in table 3.

Table 3: Panel unit root results for each variable

Series	Unit Root Method	Order	Referred Appendix	t-statistics	P-value
Audit_Committee_Size	Levin, Lin, and Chu t	Level	3(a)	-3.57705	0.0002
Board_Female_Gender_Diversity	Levin, Lin, and Chu t	Level	3(b)	-2.02329	0.0215
Board_Independence	Im, Pesaran and Shin W	Level	3(c)	-4.18407	0.0000
Board Size	Levin, Lin, and Chu t	Level	3(d)	-3.15411	0.0008
Log_Earnings_Quality	Levin, Lin, and Chu t	Level	3(e)	-6.02183	0.0000

Source: Research Analyses Output extracted

The results obtained showed that all the variables failed to align with their respective null hypotheses, which proposed in each case that the series possess unit root, and therefore is not stationary. Thus, the study concludes on the bases of the unit root results that audit committee size, board female gender diversity, board independence, board size and earnings quality are stationary at level since the results obtained and summarized on table 3 showed that all the probability values for each the series are below 5% indicating that they are all stationary at level.

Test of Hypotheses

To test the hypotheses raised in chapter one in line with the model formulated in chapter three, the fixed and random effect model of ordinary least square regression was adopted.

The fixed and random effect method of estimating panel regression does not neglect the cross section and time series nature of the data thereby taking into consideration the individuality of the several companies that make up the agricultural sector in this study. Thus, it allows for heterogeneity, which could exist among the selected companies, and this is more realistic as the various companies do not have the same outcome in their corporate governance structure and earnings quality over the years covered in by the study.

Hausman Test for Fixed/Random Effects Ordinary Least Square Regression

The Hausman test serves as a guide in the decision of which panel of ordinary least square regression is more appropriate for the estimation of the effect of corporate governance structure on earnings quality. This is achieved through the proposition of a pair of hypothesis;

So the choice of which model of regression to use in the analyses of corporate governance structures on earnings quality of the selected companies is dependent on the outcome of the Hausman test. The Hausman test result obtained in the analyses is attached as appendix 4(a) however the summary of the statistics and p-value is presented in table 4.4.

Table 4: Hausman test for fixed and random effects models

Test Summary	Chi-square statistics	P-value
Results	6.7286	0.1509

Source: Research Analyses Output extracted

The null hypothesis of the Hausman test proposed that the random effect model of the ordinary least square regression should be adopted thus on the basis of the results presented in table 4, the study accepts the null hypothesis since the probability value of the Hausman test is 0.15 approximately and it is greater than 5% threshold of rejection. So, the random effects ordinary least square regression is adopted for analyzing the effect of corporate governance structure on earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria as was initially proposed.

The random effects ordinary least square regression adopted for analyzing the hypotheses of the study is attached as appendix 4(b) to this thesis but has been summarized and presented to aid further discussion in table 5.

The residual statistics of the random effects ordinary least square regression results presented on table 4.5 suggests that the model can be relied on to explain the relationship which subsists between corporate governance structure and earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria.

Table 5: Panel random effects regression of corporate governance structures on earnings quality of agricultural companies in Nigeria

Test Statistics	Results	T-statistics	P-values
Constant	-1.7443	-2.6452	0.0130
Coefficients:			
Audit_Committee_Size	0.2292	2.2331	0.0334
Board_Female_Gender_Diversity	-0.0080	-0.6812	0.5012
Board_Independence	-0.0065	-0.7243	0.4747
Board_Size	0.1000	2.3624	0.0236
R-squared	0.3188		
Adjusted R-square	0.2249		
F-statistics	3.3932		0.0215
Durbin-Watson	2.0557		

Source: Research Analyses Output extracted

The r-squared of the random effect ordinary least square regression model is 32% approximately and shows that the model is fairly specified, indicating that the explanatory variable can explain to a fair extent the variation or the causes of change in the dependent variable which is earnings quality of the listed companies in the agricultural sector of Nigeria. The f-statistics also yielded a value of 3.393 which is significant at 5% suggesting that the corporate governance structure indicators in this study are capable of explaining the changes that occur in the earnings quality of the selected companies. Considering the Durbin-Watson statistics which returned a value of 2.0557, it can be deduced that the regression result is not hampered by serial correlation and therefore can be relied on in making decisions as it pertains to the individual hypotheses' acceptance or otherwise.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The analysis of the first hypothesis in this thesis reflects a significant influence flowing from board size of the companies within the agricultural sector to their earnings quality. The result for board size interaction with earnings quality depicts approximately

10% effect on the earnings quality of the selected companies at statistical significance level of 5% which led to the acceptance of the alternative proposition to the null hypothesis. This outcome has been similarly established by previous studies within the Nigerian economy (Olaoye and Adewumi, 2020) and specifically using thirty-seven companies selected from the manufacturing sector of the economy. Ayogu (2001) also had similar results for a study that sampled ten quoted companies from Ghanaian economy from 2010 to 2015; they concluded based on their findings that board size has a significant effect on the earnings quality of those selected companies

The analysis of the second hypothesis posited that board independence has a negative and non-significant effect on the earnings quality of companies in the agricultural sector of Nigeria. This is obviously hinged on the outcomes of the t-statistics and probability values as presented on table 5. The implication of the findings is that the board independence practiced in the sector does not influence their earnings reporting quality to an extent that is statistically relevant to make research conclusions.

The results presented on table 5 which was used in testing the third hypothesis also showed that board female gender diversity has no significant effect on the earnings quality of the selected listed companies in the agricultural sector of Nigeria. In contrast to the findings in this thesis, Olaoye and Adewumi (2020) reported that board gender diversity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria has significant influence on earnings quality. This is also the case for studies done by Zalata, Ntim, Alsohagy & Malagila (2022) which covered a time frame of 2017 to 2013 using listed companies from the Jordanian economy. The study established that board female gender diversity in consideration of female directors with financial background has significant and positive effect on earnings quality of the sampled companies. This thesis also found that audit committee size has a significant and positive effect on the earnings quality of companies in the agricultural sector of Nigeria. Similarly, Ahmed and Hasnah (2015) though the study sampled Malaysian companies, it submitted that audit committee independence influences earnings quality significantly. Peasnell, Pope and Young (2015) also found that audit committee size as an indicator of board monitoring oversight significantly decreases earnings management by managers who wish to avoid reporting losses. It is therefore obvious that there are mixed findings in similar studies considering influence corporate governance indicators on earnings quality but it is noteworthy that most studies align with this thesis on the findings made for the four corporate governance indicators; board size, independence, female gender diversity and audit committee size. However, this study maintains that the peculiarity and low development of the agricultural sector of the Nigerian economy must have contributed to the results recorded here.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIIN AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The following are the summary of the findings of this study arrived at through the test of the research hypothesis earlier formulated in this study.

1. Board size has a significant effect on the earnings quality of agricultural companies in Nigeria.
2. Board independence has no significant effect on the earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria.

3. Board female gender diversity has no significant effect on the earnings quality of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria.
4. Audit committee size significantly influences the earnings quality of the selected companies.

CONCLUSION

Corporate governance is a widely researched area of finance in developed countries. Many researchers from all over the world have come across the impact of corporate governance on earning performance. This study recognized the gap in the area of corporate governance on earning quality in Nigerian Agricultural companies. The study was carried out to examine the corporate governance and earnings quality. The study was limited to agricultural companies listed in the Nigerian exchange group. Board size, board independence, gender diversity and audit committee size were used to quantify corporate governance quality was used as the dependent variable.

The data collected were analyzed using ordinary least square panel regression analysis. The result of the analysis revealed that board size and audit committee size have significant effect on earnings quality of listed agricultural companies while board independence and gender diversity do not have significant effect on earnings quality of listed agricultural companies. Therefore, the study concludes that corporate governance in the area of size (board size and audit committee size) determines the earnings quality of agricultural companies in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

1. The study recommends the need for comprehensive evaluation of corporate governance systems of companies. Though there is yet no consensus on what number constitutes an optimal board size, the study recommends that companies with more diverse ownership interest and shareholders need to structure its board such that all key interests are represented
2. The study recommends the need for more levels of board independence. Independence board members are a key component of effective corporate governance because of the expertise and objectivity that they bring to companies.
3. The diversity issue though is gaining momentum. In corporate governance literature can still be regarded as not as dominant as compared to others especially as it relates to protecting shareholders rights and framing dividend policy. The significance of the variable nevertheless suggests that companies should strive to achieve an appropriate diversity mix.
4. There is a need to review and strengthen the composition and role of the audit committee especially as regard their monitoring and over sight function on the financial reports so as to improve the earnings quality of companies. Also, management of listed companies in Nigeria should consider the provisions of the Nigeria code of corporate governance in audit committee composition. This will improve the earnings quality of companies in Nigeria.

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